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REVIEW ON PUMPKIN SEED OIL (C. MAXIMA, C. PEPO)

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ABSTRACT

The seeds of these fruits has high source of bioactive constituents which can be used as an eatable oil and can be also be used in the pharmaceutical industries for nutraceutical. It was found to contain high amount of free fatty acids like linoleic, palmitic and stearic with their relative distribution of 43.8%, 33.1%, 13.4% and 7.8% respectively, which represents of about 98 + 0.1% of the total fatty acids amount. The dominant content of tocopherol are the γ -tocopherol where it is being predominant over α - and β - tocopherol. The antioxidant activities of the pepo seed oil indicates the good cytoprotective with the modification of few chemical compounds. The usefulness of the pepo seed oil in the management of benign prostrate may therefore become as a good medicinal product in the direct inhibition of the prostrate growth. With the investigation of hypercholesterolemia patients has been found out that it can reduce the level of total and LDL cholesterol levels by 30 – 50%. Pretreatment of the animals by PSO, then administration of the same doses of FEL produce more reduction in the arterial blood pressure ranged from 17.3"1.75 to 40.9"1.35 mmHg.

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INTRODUCTION

Pumpkin is a herb which grows and flowers during the spring seasons and bears fruits during the earlier of winter.^[1] The seeds of these fruits has high source of bioactive constituents which can be used as an eatable oil and can be also be used in the pharmaceutical industries for nutraceutical. In the recent studies there has been many documentation for the oil that were obtained from the seed of these fruit.^[2] During the literature survey there has been a lot of reports which has been focused particularly only on the composition and content of fatty acids, tocopherols and sterols in the pumpkin seed oil because of their positivity and having a good therapeutic effects for human health^[3-5]

The pepo seed oil is a dark greenish red in color and it was found that it has a high amount of free fatty acids like linoleic, palmitic and stearic with their relative distribution of 43.8%, 33.1%, 13.4% and 7.8% respectively, which represents of about 98 + 0.1% of the total fatty acids amount.^[6] the total content of the oil from the dried pumpkin seed is 41% approximately and it varies from its broad genetic.^[7]

Pepo seed oil has been used as a natural source for proteins, essential fatty acids, polyunsaturated fatty acids, also for the omega 3, 6 and 9, carotenes, lutein, vitamins such as carotenoids and β - and γ -tocopherols, phytosterols, chlorophyll, and trace elements, such as zinc and selenium^[8,9].

The eagerness for the determination of the biochemical and oxidative stability properties of pepo seed oil would valorize the value of such oil especially in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and food industries. A progress has been reached in the domain of modern medicine, we still notice the lack of efficient wounds healing treatments. The demand for natural remedies is rising in developing countries^[10] as natural substances where they could be effective, safe and cheap^[15]. Pepo seed oil has also gained an attention as an exceptional protective against many diseases like hypertension and carcinogenic diseases^[11,12] also due to its health benefits such as antidiabetic^[13], antibacterial^[14], antioxidant and antiinflammation^[4].

PHYTOCHEMISTRY OF PUMPKIN SEED OIL:

TOCOPHEROL

A portion of the extracted oil from the seeds of the cucurbita pepo was dissolved with hexane of HPLC quality for the determination of the tocopherol content in parts per million with a comparison of the standard sample where it was also prepared in the same method^[15,16] The high quality of the oil that can be obtained are from those which contains more amount of γ -tocopherol concentrations of up to 800 mg/g of the oil^[18] The most dominant content of tocopherol in pumpkin seed oil of cucurbita pepo that were found from the recent literature survey are the γ -tocopherol where it is being predominant over α - and β - tocopherol^[17] Apart from these vitamin E, the other components of vitamins and carotenoids can also be found in this oil of cucurbita pepo^[18]

MINERAL

Minerals from the pumpkin seed oil of cucurbita pepo were analyzed by different methods and the contents that obtained varies with the temperatures, climates and the environment storage. Some of the minerals that are mostly present in the pepo oil are sodium, calcium, potassium, magnesium and phosphorus and these may varies due to their culture method or culture condition.^[19] According to the recent survey there are also moderate or low source of iodine that are found in the oil which can be help in the increase of iodine intake for the patients which are having iodine deficient.^[20]

PHYTOSETROLS

The approached used for the determination of phytosterol compounds have been performed since the earlier centuries and are still the state of art technique up to date. The phytosterol compounds that are found in the pepo oil are the Δ -7-sterols rather than Δ -5-sterols and the other components include Δ 7,25- stigmastadienol (stigmasta - 7,25-dien -3 β -ol), Δ 7,22-stigmastadienol = α -spinasterol (stigmasta - 7,22- dien-3 β -ol), Δ 7,22,25-stigmastatrienol (stigmasta - 7, 22, 25-trien-3 β - ol), Δ 7-ergostenol (27- methylcholest-7-en-3 β -ol) and Δ 7,24,28-stigmastadienol = Δ 7-avenasterol (stigmasta-7, 24 (28) - dien3 β -ol)^[21, 22] But the amount of Δ -5-sterols are comparatively different between the naked and husk seed oil of the pepo seed oil.^[23]

FATTY ACID COMPOSITION

For the determination of these fatty acids the oils were converted into fatty acid methyl esters^[24] These FAME (fatty acids methyl esters) were injected into the gas chromatography and the fatty acids were compared with the retention time of the pure standard which have been analysed in the same method^[25-26] The fatty acids components that are obtained from the pepo oil are shown in the table1. In the literature survey of different papers and articles it has been found that there are many factors which influences the chemical components of these pepo seed oil like the environmental condition, the culture method or culture condition, climate and the storage conditions. Well, according to the literature survey indeed it is a rich source of linoleic acid but it is also a good source of oleic acid which are higher in comparison with the contents that are found from the other oils.^[27] The presence of the monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids can be used in the health benefit for the prevention of coronary heart disease and some other diseases^[28, 29]

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY:

Anti-Oxidant.

Tocopherols are the natural antioxidant that are found in different types of oils and are depending on the conditions they are cultivated. The quantity of total tocopherols that are present in the oils of pepo seed varies on the basis of their collection.^[32] In the recent documents the antioxidant activities were performed on different methods of antioxidant assays and the results were compared with their respected antioxidant compounds. The different methods used^[33] in the antioxidant activities are free radical DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) scavenging, soybean lipoxigenase [LOX] inhibition, ABTS radical and ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAO) assays. And the results that was documented was that the result were significantly different from each concentration with respect to the methods used and the FRAP assay was recorded as the highest 1.83 nmol/100 g FW antioxidation activity.^[34] Also in the recent articles it was found that the phosphorylated polysaccharides of pepo oils was observed by the activities of free radical DPPH, superoxide anion radical scavenging activity, reducing power and also the hydrogen peroxide that caused the damages on the rat thymic lymphocyte which showed good antioxidant in both the cell system and in *vitro*. Hence indicates the good cytoprotective with the modification of few chemical compounds.^[35]

INFLUENCE ON PROSTATE.

Pepo seed oil was claimed to be useful in the management of benign prostatic hyperplasia.^[8] The content of phytosterol in the pepo seed oil are known to interfere with the actions of dihydrotestosterone which is a potent androgen produced in the prostate by the enzyme 5 α -reductase that lead growth of the prostate plays a considerable part in the disease process of BPH, dihydrotestosterone inhibition reduced the growth of prostate.^[33] Pepo seed oil alone or combined with the phytosterol-F can results in the blockade of the T-P induced some additive blockade of the protein synthesis in the ventral lobe.^[9] In a clinical trials for the pepo oil of around 100 patients and about 96% of the patients shows no undesired side effects.^[36] Thus showed the significant effect of the pepo seed oil in improving the urinary dysfunction of the patients.^[37]

HYPERCHOLESTEROLEMIA EFFECTS

In the recent studies it has been found that plants which derived the homologous of cholesterol can be used in the cholesterol lowering effects.^[30, 38-40] Many studies had been done for the investigation of hypercholesterolemia patients which has been found out that it can reduce the level of total and LDL cholesterol levels by 30 – 50%.^[41] Plant sterols have been shown to decrease both total and LDL cholesterol levels by reducing exogenous cholesterol absorption by way of cholesterol displacement in the intestinal lumen.^[42] As described below, the mechanisms by which plant sterols lower LDL cholesterol concentrations have been shown to involve plant sterol-induced alterations in cholesterol absorption (Fig. 3) and synthesis pathways.^[38]

ANTIHYPERTENSIVE ACTIVITY

From the documentation that has been surveyed it was founded that the pepo seed oil was used as a supplementation to produced positive effect on both the non-ovariectomized and ovariectomized female rats which were analysed for the cardioprotective action and its lowering effect on the blood pressure.^[43] In the studies which had been done by Aliaa E.M.K. El-Mosallamy et al. had shown that the results detected in the ECG described that pepo seed oil treatment had yielded a significant improvement in the increased P duration, increased RR interval, and the elevated ST segment observed in the 1-NAME induced hypertensive rats.^[44] During the literature survey of Zuhair HA et al. it was found to conclude that concomitant administration of FEL (felodipine) or CPT (captopril) with natural antioxidants from the pepo seed oil can yield a beneficial therapeutic effect and retard the progression of hypertension.^[10]

Table 1. Fatty acid composition of the pumpkin seed (*Cucurbita pepo*) oil.^[30, 31,26]

Fatty acid	Content (%)
Palmitic (C _{16:0})	10.68 ± 0.42
Palmitoleic (C _{16:1})	0.58 ± 0.14
Stearic (C _{16:1})	8.67 ± 0.27
Oleic (C _{18:1})	38.42 ± 0.37
Linoleic (C _{18:2})	39.84 ± 0.08
Linolenic (C _{18:3})	0.68 0.14
Gadoleic (C _{20:1})	1.14 ± 0.00
Total saturated fatty acids	19.35 ± 0.16
Total unsaturated fatty acids	80.65 ± 0.16

Fig 1. Phytosterols.

Fig. 2. Histological sections of the ventral prostate. A Control rat. B Hyperplastic architecture of the prostate gland in a T-P (testosterone/prazosin)-treated rat.^[9]

Fig. 3. Mechanism of action by which plant sterols decrease cholesterol absorption. (1) Plant sterols reduce the amount of cholesterol incorporated into the mixed micelle. (2) Excess plant sterols are pumped out of the enterocyte via the ABC proteins, ABCG5 and ABCG8.[38]

Fig. 4. Effect of felodipine _FEL. monotherapy or combined with pumpkin seed oil _PSO. pretreatment on the arterial blood pressure of urethane-anesthetized spontaneously hypertensive rats _SHR.. i.v. administration of FEL in doses of 0.45]4 mg kgy1 body wt. decreased the arterial blood pressure by 8.11"1.71]31.75"3.06 mmHg. Pretreatment of the animals by PSO, then administration of the same doses of FEL produce more reduction in the arterial blood pressure ranged from 17.3"1.75 to 40.9"1.35 mmHg.. Values are expressed as mean"SEM, ns8 rats. _b. Significant difference from SHR group at P-0.05. _d. Significant difference from corresponding treated group at P-0.05.[10]

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